

Data documentation: Projected Abstractions and Discharges for England, 2020 to 2080, for three future scenarios

Helen Baron¹, Virginie Keller¹, Ponnambalam Rameshwaran¹, Andy Beverton², Jonny Wilson², Victoria A. Bell¹, Helen N. Davies¹, Jamie Hannaford¹.

¹ *UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Wallingford, Oxfordshire, OX10 8BB, UK*

² *Environment Agency, Horizon House, Deanery Road, Bristol, BS1 5AH*

Correspondence: Helen Baron (heron@ceh.ac.uk)

Abstract

This document describes datasets of projected monthly abstractions and annual discharges for England on a 1 km × 1 km resolution, for the years 2020 to 2080 for three future scenarios: Economic Growth (EG), Business as Usual (BaU), and Sustainable (Sus).

These datasets draw on various publicly available water demand projections, combining values and growth factors across different water use sectors, to create coherent sets of future scaling factors for three socio-economic scenarios. These factors are then applied to baseline abstraction and discharge datasets, based on Environment Agency (EA) information and the Water Resources Geographic Information System (WRGIS 2017) respectively, to produce abstraction and discharge projections which can be used to better understand the interplay between humans and water under different potential future scenarios.

The datasets are available on CEDA: Baron et al. [2025].

1 Introduction

A set of future projections for abstraction and discharge data for England on a 1 km × 1 km resolution, for the years 2020 to 2080, have been produced by applying scaling factors to baseline abstraction and discharge datasets [Rameshwaran et al., 2024b]. The scaling factors were derived from previous studies, including the Environment Agency's (EA's) National Framework [EA, 2020], the Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA) report on future demand outside the water industry [Wood, 2020], and the Joint Environmental Programme (JEP) scenarios for water use in power production [Moores, 2022]. The scaling factors were applied nationally or regionally for each year, according to the type of water user, e.g. Public Water Supply (PWS), irrigation, energy, or industry.

Three scenarios were produced to capture a range of possible socio-economic futures, as described in Baron et al. [2023]:

- “Economic Growth” (EG)
- “Business as Usual” (BaU)
- “Sustainability” (Sus)

For each of these scenarios, two datasets have been produced:

- Projected monthly abstractions ($\text{m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$) from 2020 to 2080 for Groundwater (GW), and Surface water (SW) sources,
- Projected daily rate of discharges ($\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$), varying annually, from 2020 to 2080.

All datasets are on a $1\text{ km} \times 1\text{ km}$ grid for England and are available in CSV format.

These datasets can be applied in future hydrological and water resource modelling, and have been used in the CS-N0W project ([Climate services for a Net Zero resilient world - GOV.UK](#)) to determine the impact of anthropogenic influences on future river flows [Bell et al., 2023] and to identify potential future water resource challenges [Tanguy et al., 2023]. CS-N0W: Gridded future projections of natural and artificially influenced river flows (1980 to 2080) are available on CEDA [Rameshwaran et al., 2025b,a].

2 Methods

2.1 Baseline data

2.1.1 Abstractions

The starting data for the future abstractions are the mean monthly reported abstracted values for England at $1\text{ km} \times 1\text{ km}$ resolution, available for the years 1999 to the end of 2014 from Rameshwaran et al. [2024b]. A five year average (2010 to 2014 inclusive) was used as a baseline dataset as it was deemed to be the best approximation for recent abstraction patterns given the available data.

This data contains information on the purpose of each abstraction: each abstraction has an associated Primary purpose (these are broad categories such as agriculture or water supply), with further detail provided by the Secondary purpose (see Rameshwaran et al. [2024a] for more information). For example, the Primary category “Agriculture” contains the Secondary categories: Aquaculture-Fish, Aquaculture-Plant, Forestry, General Agriculture, Horticulture & Nurseries, Orchards, Zoos/Kennels/Stables. Finally, each abstraction has a Use purpose which gives additional information, and can be used to estimate the proportion of each water abstraction that is consumed (e.g. by evaporation) rather than returned to the system (e.g. by artificial discharges). These purpose categories were used to group the baseline abstractions by water use sector so that sector-specific scaling factors could be applied, as future water use is projected to change at different rates for different water use sectors. The specific groupings were chosen to reflect the different sectors for which future projections have been made in existing studies (see Table 1).

2.1.2 Discharges

The baseline data for the future discharges are the mean Recent Actual (RACT) discharges available from Rameshwaran et al. [2024b], these data were retrieved from the Water Resources Geographic Information System (WRGIS 2017) and are either an average over 2007 to 2012, or 2010 to 2015, or an estimation from consented dry weather flow if discharge time series are not available (there is no record of which method was used to derive each data point). The discharge data is available at $1\text{ km} \times 1\text{ km}$ resolution for England, with some cross-border data from Natural Resources Wales (NRW), and includes artificial discharges to water bodies such as outflow from sewage treatment works (STW) and discharges from industry. Discharges of less than $20\text{ m}^3\text{ day}^{-1}$ are generally excluded, though smaller discharges can be included in headwater catchments.

The discharge data contains information on the water use sector associated with each discharge but, unlike the abstraction data, discharge purposes were recorded as free text input so are very difficult to categorise (see Section 2.3.2). Additionally, discharges are often combinations, e.g. SEWAGE & TRADE COMBINED - UNSPECIFIED.

2.2 Construction of scaling factors

2.2.1 Abstractions

Scaling factors for each year and water use sector were sourced from existing studies, Table 1 summarises the data used to create the different scaling factors for each scenario. Data from the DEFRA report [Wood, 2020] on the growth of non-PWS demands were available as ‘growth factors’ for the year 2050 (from baseline data averaged over the period 2010 to 2015), so this study has linearly interpolated these growth factors from 2016 to 2050, and kept them constant from 2050 to 2080. Data from the JEP report [Moore, 2022] was available as estimated fresh water abstractions for power production (not including hydropower) in Ml/d from 2018 to 2050, these were converted to scaling factors using the baseline values of water abstraction for power production, and kept constant from 2050 to 2080. Data from the National Framework [EA, 2020] was available as an excel workbook¹ which extracts estimated PWS abstractions for each Water Resource Zone (WRZ) from the the water companies’ water resource management plans (WRMP19) under different population projections, Per Capita Consumption (PCC), and leakage reduction targets. This workbook was used to extract estimated PWS abstractions for each WRZ from 2020 to 2080 for the EG, BaU and Sus scenarios (as detailed in Table 1). These were converted to scaling factors using the baseline values of water abstraction for PWS for each WRZ.

¹[NF_SDB_Model_210325.xlsx](#), provided to UKCEH by the EA on 08/09/2022 via email

Water use sector	Source of scaling factor	EG scaling	BaU scaling	Sus scaling
Chemicals	DEFRA report [Wood, 2020]	“Uncontrolled demand, Regionalisation” growth factor	Best estimate growth factor	“Sustainable, Regionalisation” growth factor
Paper & Pulp	DEFRA report [Wood, 2020]	“Uncontrolled demand, Regionalisation” growth factor	Best estimate growth factor	“Sustainable, Regionalisation” growth factor
Food & Drink	DEFRA report [Wood, 2020]	“Uncontrolled demand, Regionalisation” growth factor	Best estimate growth factor	“Sustainable, Regionalisation” growth factor
Spray Irrigation	DEFRA report [Wood, 2020]	“Uncontrolled demand, Regionalisation” growth factor	Best estimate growth factor	“Sustainable, Regionalisation” growth factor
Power	JEP report [Moores, 2022]	Freshwater use for FES21 scenario “Steady Progression”	Freshwater use for FES21 scenario “System Transformation”	Freshwater use for FES21 scenario “Leading the Way”
PWS	National Framework [EA, 2020]	High population scenario. PCC of 127 l/p/d, 30% leakage reduction by 2050	Central population scenario. PCC and leakage reduction from WRMP19	Low population scenario. PCC of 110 l/p/d, 50% leakage reduction by 2050

Table 1: Details on the creation of scaling factors for the three scenarios: “Economic Growth” (EG), “Business as Usual” (BaU), “Sustainability” (Sus). FES21: Future Energy Scenarios (2021). PCC: Per Capita Consumption. WRMP19: Water Resource Management Plan (2019).

2.2.2 Discharges

For the majority of the water use sectors, the scaling factors produced for the abstractions were also applied to the discharges. However, for the PWS sector new scaling factors were calculated to ensure that any reduction in leakage would be accurately represented (i.e. if leakage levels are reduced then abstractions are reduced but discharges remain the same, since the same volume of water is being provided to the end user). To construct PWS scaling factors for discharge data, the change in water reaching the end user was calculated using data from the National Framework workbook for each WRZ. Specifically, values for *PWS – leakage* were extracted for each WRZ for the years 2020 to 2080, then divided by the baseline values of *PWS – leakage* (available for the years 2016 or 2017 depending on the WRZ) to give annual scaling factors.

2.3 Application of scaling factors

2.3.1 Abstractions

To produce future estimates, it was necessary to group the baseline abstractions by water use sector and by WRZ. Each point abstraction was allocated a WRZ using a spatial join method with shapefiles for WRZs (as used in the

WRMP19). Water use sector was determined by the primary use description, secondary and tertiary use codes listed in the baseline abstraction files (columns ‘Primary Description’, ‘Secondary Code’ and ‘Use Code’ respectively). Prior to grouping, some of the secondary codes were altered to better match their use as detailed in ‘Use Description’, following the method described in Appendix A of the DEFRA report [Wood, 2020]. The groupings for each water sector scaling are described in Table 2. The scaling factors were then applied to the relevant abstractions to produce monthly estimated abstractions from 2020 to 2080. Any water use sector not covered by the scaling factors was assumed to stay constant. Tidal Water abstractions were discarded, since the scaling factors were designed for freshwater usage (e.g. the JEP report [Moore, 2022] only calculates freshwater use in the power sector), and the majority of water resource models are only concerned with freshwater usage.

Water use sector	Primary Description	Secondary Code	Use Code	Spatial Application
Chemicals	any	CHE	any	National
Paper & Pulp	any	PAP	any	National
Food & Drink	any	FAD, BRW, DAR	any, and 460, 470 for any secondary code	National
Spray Irrigation	Agriculture	any	380, 390, 400, 410, 420	National
Power	any	ELC, MEC	all except 240 (hydropower)	National
PWS	any	PWS, WAT	any	WRZ

Table 2: Details on water use sector groupings for abstraction scaling factors, descriptions of the use codes can be found in Appendix A in Rameshwaran et al. [2024a]

2.3.2 Discharges

The application of the scaling factors to the discharge data was considerably more challenging due to the fact that the discharge purposes were recorded as free text input; water use sectors were allocated based on this field as best as possible (see Appendix A for details), but many discharges were assumed to remain constant due to the ambiguity of the discharge purpose. About half of the total discharges were assumed to remain constant (50% of the recorded discharge points, 42% of the total discharge volume), either because their purpose is unclear or because they fall into a category with a constant scaling factor (e.g. industry outside of Chemicals, Paper & Pulp, or Food & Drink). For discharges determined to be related to PWS, the scaling factors were applied by WRZ using the same method as used for the abstractions.

3 Summary of Datasets

3.1 Datasets

For each of the three future scenarios (EG, BaU, Sus) there are two datasets in CSV format:

- Time series of projected monthly abstractions ($\text{m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$) from 2020 to 2080 on a $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid (Easting and Northing at grid-box centre), with information on primary, secondary, and use descriptions for each source (GW and SW),
- Projected daily discharge rates ($\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$) from 2020 to 2080 on a $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid (Easting and Northing at grid-box centre), with discharge purpose description.

Table 3 shows the file naming conventions.

Type	Future Scenario	File name
Monthly abstractions, 2020 to 2080, $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$, multiple purposes, GW & SW sources	EG	England_Monthly_Abstractions_1km_GW_SW_EG_202001_208012.csv
	BaU	England_Monthly_Abstractions_1km_GW_SW_BaU_202001_208012.csv
	Sus	England_Monthly_Abstractions_1km_GW_SW_Sus_202001_208012.csv
Annual discharge rates, 2020 to 2080, $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$	EG	England_Daily_Rate_Discharges_1km_EG_2020_2080.csv
	BaU	England_Daily_Rate_Discharges_1km_BaU_2020_2080.csv
	Sus	England_Daily_Rate_Discharges_1km_Sus_2020_2080.csv

Table 3: File naming convention

3.1.1 Abstractions

The projected abstraction datasets provide information on:

- Abstraction location (Easting, Northing)
- Abstraction purpose (see Appendix Tables A1-3 in Rameshwaran et al. [2024a]):
 - Primary purpose (character string)
 - Secondary purpose (character string)
 - Use purpose (integer)
- Source (character string)
- Monthly projected abstracted water volume (real number, $\text{m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$)

The projected monthly abstractions are provided at a $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ resolution for England for 2020 to 2080, and have a specified abstraction source (SW or GW) and a purpose detailed by the Primary, Secondary, and Use purposes categories (drawn from the abstraction licences, see Section 2.1.1). Each Use purpose has an associated estimated

loss: high (100%), medium (60%), low (3%), or very low (0.3%), which indicates how much of the abstracted water is assumed to be consumed (e.g. through evaporation), see Table A3 in Rameshwaran et al. [2024a]. It should be noted that, in their application of both the baseline and the future projected abstractions, Bell et al. [2023] assume that most of the water from very low loss abstractions is returned immediately to the water source and is not accounted for in the discharge dataset (this is investigated further in Rameshwaran et al. [2022]).

3.1.2 Discharges

The projected discharge datasets provide information on:

- Consented discharge location (Easting, Northing)
- Discharge impact location (Easting, Northing), this matches the consented discharge location unless the point of impact falls in a different WRGIS water body
- Purpose of discharge (character string)
- Projected discharge rate (real number, $\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$)

The projected annual discharge rates are provided at $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ resolution for England, with some cross-border data from NRW, for 2020 to 2080. Discharge purpose is provided, and has been derived from the WRGIS dataset with some simplification applied to aid the spatial grouping (see Rameshwaran et al. [2024a] for details).

4 Data Limitations and Uncertainties

These datasets have been produced to aid future water resource planning in a national context, but they have various intrinsic limitations and uncertainties that any user should be aware of:

- Since these datasets are derived from other datasets, they inherit the uncertainties of the original datasets (see Section 8 in Rameshwaran et al. [2024a]);
- To create and apply spatially varying scaling factors, it was assumed that PWS abstractions and discharges are related to the WRZ that they are located in. This is not always accurate (for example, water abstracted from a reservoir will often supply multiple WRZs). However, this is a necessary assumption as it is incredibly difficult to trace water from abstraction point to user, and from user to discharge point.
- The scaling factors were derived from multiple studies that were not designed to be used in conjunction, this introduces uncertainties from the merging of the scenarios in each study (see Baron et al. [2023] for information on how this was managed) and also means that the factors for each water sector are independent. In reality, changes in demand from one user for a particular water source would influence, and be influenced by, competing users, but this level of complexity is well beyond the scope of these projections.
- The use of scaling factors assumes that each abstraction and discharge point can increase or decrease without limitation, it also assumes that all future demand and discharge will be met from current abstraction and discharge points (i.e. all existing abstraction/discharge points will continue to operate with no new ones created). This is a necessary simplification.
- Applying scaling factors at an annual timestep neglects any potential change to seasonal patterns of water use and discharge.

- Due to challenges in obtaining data, the baseline datasets are already a decade old, so do not reflect more recent water usage and discharge patterns. Some of the data used to produce the scaling factors has also been superseded (i.e. water resource management plans for 2024 have since been released). This is an inherent weakness of future projections, and to mitigate this the code used to produce the projected abstractions has been made available [Baron, 2025] so that updated future projections can be more easily constructed.
- While the abstraction and discharge datasets can be used together (see Bell et al. [2023]), care should be taken when doing this. The baseline datasets are not entirely compatible: abstractions are monthly while discharges are annual; abstractions cover the period 2010 to 2014 inclusive while discharges are averaged for a six year period prior to 2017 (see Section 2.1); and it is not always clear how much of the return flow from any abstraction is accounted for in the discharge data and how much is returned to the abstraction point. It was also difficult to apply the scaling factors in a similar way across abstractions and discharges due to the ambiguity of the discharge purpose (see Section 2.3.2).

5 Acknowledgements

This data publication is supported by the Natural Environment Research Council award number NE/X019063/1 as part of the Hydro-JULES programme delivering National Capability. The dataset is also linked with the Climate Services for a Net Zero Resilient World (CS-N0W) project commissioned by the UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ). We acknowledge use of data from data licences granted to us by the Environment Agency to help generate new outputs and information for CS-N0W. The authors would like to thank the Environment Agency and their staff for supplying the National Framework workbook, and their help in applying it to this work. Thanks to Andrew Moores (RWE Generation UK) for his support in applying his modelled output to this work.

References

- H. Baron. github repository: CS-N0W FAS, 2025. URL https://github.com/HEBaron/CS-NOW_FAS.
- H. Baron, V. Keller, J. Hannaford, and V. Bell. Approaches to construct scenarios of future water demand – d2: Future water availability for water intensive energy infrastructure. climate services for a net zero resilient world (CS-N0W) report, June 2023. URL <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/672b50a040f7da695c921bf3/cs-now-d2-future-water-resources-scenarios.pdf>.
- H. Baron, V. Keller, P. Rameshwaran, A. Beverton, J. Wilson, V. Bell, H. Davies, and J. Hannaford. Gridded projections of ground and surface water abstraction and discharge for England 2020-2080, 2025. URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/4731f72a886c47739fb5990c379c91dd>.
- V. Bell, P. Rameshwaran, H. Davies, H. Baron, V. Keller, and J. Hannaford. Hydrological modelling and artificial influences: performance assessment future scenarios: Cs-now-d2 future water availability for water intensive energy infrastructure. climate services for a net zero resilient world (CS-N0W) report, June 2023. URL <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/672b4ff0f03408fa7966d1e5/cs-now-d2-future-water-resources-hydrological-modelling.pdf>.
- EA. Meeting our future water needs: a national framework for water resources, 2020.
- A. Moores. Scenarios for the projection to 2050 of Water Use by Power Producers - updated using FES21, 2022.

- P. Rameshwaran, V. Bell, M. Brown, H. Davies, A. Kay, A. C. Rudd, and C. Sefton. Use of abstraction and discharge data to improve the performance of a national-scale hydrological model. *Water resources research*, 58, 2022. URL <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR029787>.
- P. Rameshwaran, V. Bell, H. Davies, P. Sadler, A. Beverton, and R. Thornton. Data documentation: Gridded actual abstraction, discharge and hands-off flow datasets for england., 2024a. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13746897>.
- P. Rameshwaran, V. Bell, H. Davies, P. Sadler, A. Beverton, R. Thornton, and M. Rhodes-Smith. Gridded actual abstraction, discharge and hands-off flow datasets for england., 2024b. URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/18886f95ba84447f997efac96df456ad>.
- P. Rameshwaran, V. Bell, H. Davies, H. Baron, V. Keller, and J. Hannaford. Data documentation: Gridded future projections of natural and artificially influenced river flows (1980 to 2080), 2025a. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10958783>.
- P. Rameshwaran, V. Bell, H. Davies, H. Baron, V. Keller, J. Hannaford, and M. Rhodes-Smith. Cs-n0w: Gridded future projections of natural and artificially influenced river flows (1980 to 2080), 2025b. URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/cf66055440344d7eb9b6f834e81736c6>.
- M. Tanguy, J. B. V. R. P. Magee, E. and Hannaford, H. Baron, V. Keller, and L. Barker. Analysis on future scenarios – d2: Future water resources for water intensive energy infrastructure. climate services for a net zero resilient world (CS-N0W) report, June 2023. URL <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/672b4fbbabb279b2de1e8c34/cs-now-d2-future-water-resources-output-analysis.pdf>.
- Wood. Understanding future water demand outside of the water industry, 2020.

Appendix A

To create future discharge scenarios, scaling factors were applied to baseline discharge data. The scaling factors vary by water use sector and, for Public Water Supply (PWS), by location. The scaling factors were drawn from previous studies and fall into six sector categories: Chemicals, Paper & Pulp, Food & Drink, Spray Irrigation, Power, and PWS. The baseline discharges have an associated discharge purpose, these were grouped into each water use sector according to the following (note that there are no discharges associated with Spray Irrigation):

- Chemicals: CHEMICAL MANUFACTURER; BASIC IND. CHEMICALS INORGANIC; BASIC IND. CHEMICALS ORGANIC
- Paper & Pulp: PULP PAPER AND BOARD
- Food & Drink: PREP OF MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS; TREATED DAIRY WASTE; CREAMERY; BREWING AND MALTING; SEWAGE AND TRADE EFFLUENT CONSISTING OF CIDER PROCESSING WAT; MISCELLANEOUS FOODS; BREAD/CONFECTIONERY; SUGAR AND SUGAR PRODUCTS
- Power: NUCLEAR FUEL PRODUCTION & WASTE PR; ENERGY SUPPLIER; PRODUCTION AND DISTRIBUTION OF ELECTRICITY

- PWS: SEWAGE TREATMENT WORKS; SEWAGE DISCHARGES - FINAL/TREATED EFFLUENT - WATER COMPANY; TRADE DISCHARGES - PROCESS EFFLUENT - WATER COMPANY (WTW); SEWAGE DISCHARGES-FINAL/TREATED EFFLUENT - WATER COMPANY; CRUDE SEWAGE; DOMESTIC PROPERTY (MULTIPLE); SEWAGE TREATMENT PLANT: SEWAGE DISCHARGES - STW STORM OVERFLOW/STORM TANK - WATER CO; SEWAGE DISCHARGE; SEWERAGE NETWORK; WASTE WATER TREATMENT WORKS; WATER TREATMENT WORKS; SEWAGE DISPOSAL WORKS; SEWAGE DISCHARGES - FINAL/TREATED EFFLUENT: DOMESTIC PROPERTY (SINGLE): DOMESTIC PROPERTY; SEWERAGE NETWORK - SEWERS - WATER COMPANY; SEWERAGE NETWORK - PUMPING STATION - WATER COMPANY; SEWERAGE NETWORK - PUMPING STATION: WATER SUPPLY GRID; PWS FINAL EFFLUENT: FINAL EFFLUENT: SECONDARY TREATED EFFLUENT: FINAL/TREATED EFFLUENT WATER; SEWAGE EFFLUENT: SEWAGE - WATER COMPANY: WTP: DOMESTIC SEWAGE: SEWAGE DISCHARGES - FINAL/TREATED EFFLUENT - WATER COMPANY &; SEWAGE WORKS EFFLUENT; TREATED SEWAGE EFFLUENT AND SETTLED STORM SEWAGE; DOMESTIC: TREATED EFFLUENT; SECONDARY TREATED SEWAGE EFFLUENT AND STORM SEWAGE EFFLUENT; SEWAGE IN AN EMERGENCY AND STORM SEWAGE: TREATED SEWAGE EFFLUENT AND STORM SEWAGE EFFLUENT; STORM SEWAGE EFFLUENT AND SEWAGE IN AN EMERGENCY; SEWAGE DISCHARGES - PUMPING STATION - WATER COMPANY; SEWAGE TREATMENT; TREATED SEWAGE EFFLUENT NOT CONTAINING TRADE; BIOLOGICALLY TREATED SEWAGE EFFLUENT; SEWAGE DISCHARGES - SEWER STORM OVERFLOW - WATER COMPANY; BERKHAMSTED SEWAGE WORKS - BULLBE